

ESTIMATION OF COBALT BY BENZIMIDAZOLE

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A new method for the estimation of cobalt has been established. Cobalt is precipitated as $\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2)_2$ by aqueous benzimidazole at p_{H} 10. The precipitate is dried at 105° and weighed as such. The compound contains 20.12% cobalt. Cobalt can be estimated by this method in the presence of barium and calcium.

It has been reported by one of us (this *Journal*, 1951, 18, 710) that cobalt^{II} forms with benzimidazole an unusually stable complex of brilliant violet colour. The complex is of the "same type as that formed by nickel with dimethylglyoxime. It is sparingly soluble in water, and, when dried at 105° , has the constant composition, $\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{N}_2)_2$, containing 20.12% cobalt. The precipitation is complete at p_{H} 10 and the precipitate is made easily filtrable in presence of a small amount of potassium sulphate.

The cobalt complex was subjected to thermogravimetric analysis to ascertain the proper temperature for drying. From the thermolysis graph (Fig. 1) it can be seen that the complex starts decomposing at about 100° . The amount of decomposition is extremely small till 120° for a macro-scale analysis; so a drying temperature of 105° is recommended to minimise the time of drying.

FIG. 1

In order to compare this method with the standard electrolytic and "cobalt sulphate" methods, a statistical analysis of the data was made, and it was found out to be equally efficient. As the precipitation is done at p_{H} 10, all elements, forming insoluble hydroxide, must be absent. Common anions were found not to interfere when not present in large excess. Estimation of cobalt can be more easily done by this method than the two standard methods, referred to above. The reagent can also be very easily prepared.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzimidazole was prepared according to the method of Wundt (*Ber.*, 1878, 11, 826). *o*-Phenylenediamine (54 g.) was heated with 90% formic acid (32 c.c.) on a water-bath for 2 hours. The mixture was then treated with 10% caustic soda till alkaline. The liberated benzimidazole was filtered and purified by recrystallisation from hot water, m. p. $171-72^\circ$. Approximately 1% solution of the reagent was obtained by dissolving the requisite amount in warm distilled water and filtering off any insoluble residue. Such a solution was found to keep well for over 4 weeks.

A standard cobalt solution was prepared by dissolving cobalt chloride of analytical grade (B. D. H.) in water. The stock solution was standardised both by electrodepositing the cobalt and by converting the chloride into sulphate and weighing as anhydrous cobalt sulphate.

For estimation, a known amount of the standard cobalt solution was taken in a 500 c.c. Jena beaker and the volume was made up to about 150 c.c. with water. To the solution was added 2 g. of A. R. potassium sulphate. The reagent solution was then added in 100 % excess. The mixture was rendered alkaline (p_H 10, tested with p_H paper) with dilute ammonia. It was thoroughly stirred and digested for $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour on the water-bath. The precipitate was then filtered in a sintered glass Gooch crucible of medium porosity (Jena 1 G 3). The precipitate was thoroughly washed with warm water till free of chloride, and dried in an air-oven at 105° to a constant weight. The results of analysis are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Co taken.	Co found.	Diff.	Co taken.	Co found.	Diff.
0.0630 g.	0.0628 g.	- 0.0002	0.0218 g.	0.0221 g.	+ 0.0003
0.0605	0.0607	+ 0.0002	0.0169	0.0168	- 0.0001
0.0605	0.0606	+ 0.0001	0.0169	0.0167	- 0.0002
0.0327	0.0328	+ 0.0001	0.0121	0.0118	- 0.0003
0.0285	0.0283	- 0.0002	0.0121	0.0118	- 0.0003

It was found that cobalt could be correctly estimated by this method when present between the limit of 63 and 12 mg.

Following is the statistical analysis of the above data :

$$\bar{x} = (-0.00013 + 0.00097) 1/10 = -0.00006.$$

To find the standard deviation, s ,

$$\begin{aligned} (n-1) s^2 &= \sum x_i^2 - nx^2 \\ &= 0.00000046 - 0.000000036 \\ &= 0.000000424 \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} s^2 &= 0.00000004711 \\ s &= 0.000215 \text{ correctly.} \end{aligned}$$

If the method were to give correct result, we have $\mu \doteq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Now } t &= \frac{|\bar{x} - \mu|}{s} \sqrt{n} = \frac{0.00006 \times 3.162}{0.000215} \\ &= 0.8824 \text{ on 9 degrees of freedom.} \end{aligned}$$

The probability that this value of t will be exceeded numerically, in random analysis, is more than 0.50; the value is thus not significant. Hence the method is equally suitable as the methods for standardisation. Any error is due to chance factor.

Estimation of Cobalt in presence of Barium and Calcium.—Here ammonia used for the precipitation was freshly prepared to avoid the precipitation of carbonate

TABLE II

Co taken.	Taken.	Found.	Co found.
0.0242 g.	Ba 0.0122 g.	Ba 0.0121 g.	0.0243
0.0242	Ca 0.0093	Ca 0.0091	0.0243

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